

Ferroelectric and Piezoelectric Properties of (Ba_{0.95}Ca_{0.05})(Ti_{0.92}Zr_{0.04}Sn_{0.04})O₃ Lead-Free Electroceramic

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Abstract

The lead-free (Ba_{0.95}Ca_{0.05})(Ti_{0.92}Zr_{0.04}Sn_{0.04})O₃ (BCZST) electroceramic was prepared by solid state reaction method; investigated ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties. The formation of perovskite structure without any secondary phase suggesting that Ca²⁺, Sn⁴⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ well diffused in BaTiO₃ lattice to form a solid solution. The dense microstructure with an average grain size of 23.5 μm is observed having relative density ~ 95%. Temperature dependent dielectric measurement shows the dielectric maxima at Curie temperature, T_c = 92 °C with ε_r = 8142. Polarization measurement to an applied electric field exhibit the typical hysteresis loop with P_r = 5.83 μC/cm² and E_c = 2.45 kV/cm, which confirms the ferroelectric nature of BCZST. The poled BCZST sample exhibits the direct piezoelectric coefficient d₃₃ = 296 pC/N and converse piezoelectric coefficient d₃₃* = 268 pm/V. The present BCZST ceramic with moderate ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties can be useful for developing the piezoelectric devices.

Keywords - Ferroelectric, Piezoelectric, BaTiO₃, Piezoelectric coefficient